

1 **TCF-associated TLE co-repressor function in trophectoderm specification in embryogenesis.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of TLE5
8 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the
9 human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Patel, S.R., Bhumbra, S.S., Paknikar, R.S. and Dressler, G.R., 2012. Epigenetic mechanisms of
12 Groucho/Grg/TLE mediated transcriptional repression. Molecular cell, 45(2), pp.185-195.
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